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Investigating the Use of ICT Among English Language Lecturers of Some Tertiary Institutions in Northwestern Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The study seeks to find out the integration of ICT in teaching English language in polytechnics and colleges of education in North Western Nigeria. The study also aimed at finding out whether ICT utilization among lecturers is gender sensitive in the region. The descriptive survey design was employed using 231 respondents. The structured questionnaire was administered and chi-square statistics was used through SPSS to test null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significant. Findings of the study revealed that gender does not any significant influence lecturers' performance in the ICT utilization. In other words, male and female do not differ significantly in their level of ICT utilization. It was also found that there was low ICT utilisation among English lecturers from colleges of education and polytechnics in the area of study. The researcher recommended that English lecturers should intensify their efforts toward using available tools in their environment to enhance their job. It was also recommended that tertiary institutions regulatory bodies such as NBTE and NCCE should be proactive to ensure enabling ICT environment in all the institutions under their supervision.

Keywords: descriptive survey design, English lecturers, ICT Utilisation, SPSS, Tertiary Institutions

INTRODUCTION

The current saturation of possible synchronous software platforms that foreign language teachers can utilize is challenging the traditional classroom. At the same time, these virtual platforms are having a profound effect on current pedagogical practices that are not yet firmly entrenched in foreign language teacher development programs. A number of issues arise whenever an instructor chooses to implement such a tool (or circumstances require its implementation). These issues include logistics, preference for platform choice, student concerns, computer/device specifications and customization options. On top of these practical concerns, these cultural factors, teacher abilities (through training and otherwise), multi-modality adjustments, and virtual adaptations influence the success or failure for the implementation journey. One area in particular poses a significant challenge for both learners and teachers alike in a foreign language-learning environment. The development of sociolinguistic competence is a necessary skill for successfully navigating through synchronous environments. After completing a historical review of the term sociolinguistic competence, I investigate the manner in which sociolinguistic skills influence the language acquisition process. This editorial includes investigations into how teacher training and technological skills influence and enable the acquisition of sociolinguistic competence within the tools and the target language in virtual classroom spaces through these guiding questions for synchronous virtual classrooms, language learning and foreign language teacher development.

The objectives of tertiary education in Nigeria like polytechnic, is to train higher skill manpower such as technologists and technicians which are relevant to the needs, aspirations and the development of the nation's diverse economy and industries. On the colleges of education, the objectives are to produce teachers with strong moral values, self-reliance and entrepreneurial capabilities for the social and economic benefit of themselves and the Nigerian society.

For the lecturers of these institutions to carry out their job efficiently and effectively especially in this age of knowledge-based technology and globalization, the use of information and communication technology (ICT) becomes imperative. It is interest to note that, tertiary institutions all over the world are rapidly incorporating information and communication technology (ICT) into all facets of teaching, research and management. Teachers who succeed in making use of ICT in their work processes do not only contribute to improve learning outcomes in their students, but also benefit personally from enhanced work productivity (Carlson & Gadio, 2000).

Lecturers from Colleges of education and polytechnics have various tasks to accomplish and these range from teaching, research and publications, marking of tests and examinations, supervising students' research activities, supporting students through advisory roles, attending conferences, providing community services etc. For them to deliver well and be just to the teeming technological youths in their institutions, there is need for them to make effective integration of ICT in their respective lessons. This is necessary in order to meet up with the demands of their job. Jusuf (2005) and Daniel (2002) reported that overwhelming majority of teachers in Europe use ICT to plan lessons more effectively and more efficiently. With the use of ICT, teachers have also been able to communicate and collaborate with other teachers and this enhances their job performance.

ICT can provide a considerable benefit in supporting learning. By using technology in their learning, the students can be active learners. They will be aware of what information they need, why they need it, and how they can get that information. As mentioned by Bransford, Brown, and Cocking (cited in Huffaker, 2003, p. 357) an active learning allows the students to decide when they require a particular information and whether they have already understood that information or not. This active learning also implies an independent learning.

By having access to internet in their school the students will not totally depend on the teachers. They can explore information available in the internet, find information that they need, copy it, and go on to find more and more information. By using this learning system, the students also become self-managed in their learning process. As noted by Jarold and Sue (1992, p. 50) self-managed learning allows the students to be self-motivated and self-directed learners who will be able to readily, efficiently, and quickly respond to the quick change of information. The use of blog, for instance, can allow the lecturers and students to be very up-to-date to the lessons.

Statement of the Problem

In this era of globalization, job performance of academic staff in higher institutions cannot be separated from the level of ICT proficiency which is necessary for quality academic output. Unfortunately, some higher institution lecturers still do not recognize the opportunities that ICT presents for improving the efficiency and effectiveness of their job. Some of them lack knowledge that would aid the application of ICT skills in instructional delivery, research and record management. This results in the utilization of ICT among teachers in the teaching/learning situation being low (Yusuf, 2005). Research reports have shown that overwhelming majority of teachers in Europe use ICT to plan lessons more efficiently (Yusuf, 2005 & Daniel, 2002). Although, researches have been carried out on the impact of ICT competence on job efficacy of teachers in the western world, little or no researches have been done in this area in Nigeria. This study therefore, investigated the extent to which lecturers' level of ICT competence influence their job efficacy.

Objectives of the Study

Purpose of the study

The main objective of this study is to investigate the ICT utilization among English Language lecturers in colleges of education and polytechnics in North West Zone of Nigeria. Therefore, the objectives are to:

- i. Find out the difference in the level of ICT utilization between English lecturers from polytechnics and colleges of education in the North West Zone Nigeria.

Find out the difference in the level of ICT utilization between male and female English lecturers in the North West Zone Nigeria.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Information and communication technology (ICT) encompasses the effective use of equipment and programs to access, retrieve, convert, store, organize, manipulate and present data and information (Gay & Blades, 2005). The use of ICT has been found by researchers to improve job efficiency and effectiveness of teachers. Wheeler (2000) discovered in his study that the use of ICT improves efficiency in educational process and effects changes in teaching methodology, assessment of learning, student tracking, communication and evaluation. Thus, the use of ICT by university teachers reduces workload (Omenyi, Aju & Odimegwu, 2007). In support of this finding Balanskat, Blamire and Kefala (2006) reported that ICT is being increasingly used by teachers in their day-to-day work leading to increased efficiency in planning and preparation of work. Similarly, Holdich (2002) reported that ICT programs like web-based and computer-based analysis of written works save the time the teacher spend in marking students' scripts. Thus, in this era of information and communication technology, institutions should start investing in modern educational technologies which will provide innovative learning environment where both teachers and students could move beyond the limits of school building for information, interaction and enrichment. This is what job efficiency of university lecturers is all about. According to Becta (2004), ICT equips teachers with new innovations in education and in teaching and research.

The researcher attributed these findings to the fact that the majority of the female academicians used in the study were younger than their male counterparts. Thus younger age has been found to be associated with more favorable attitudes towards ICT (Jennings & Onwugbuzie 2001) Yusuf (2005) and Olulube (2006) in their studies showed that teacher ICT competence in Nigeria is below expectation and access to ICT resources like the internet and computer is mostly limited in campuses of various higher institutions. This finding is supported by the work of Akpan (2008) who reported that lecturers' perception of the role of ICT in management of university education was significantly low. The implication of these findings is that the level of university teachers' ICT competence could greatly impact upon their job efficiency in classroom teaching, communication, students' record keeping, and research/ publication.

In a study conducted by Omenyi, Agu and Odimegwu (2007), it was found that on the average, teachers feel that ICT have helped them to increase their classroom efficiency. They also discovered in their study that teachers' perception of their increased job efficiency was associated with the level of ICT competence possessed by the teachers. This finding suggests that ICT is effective in providing educational delivery to students. In a related study, Soffer and Raban (2003) and Ramajah, Jantan and Aafagi (2003) discovered a significant difference in ICT competence between male and female teachers. This finding was supported by the work of Dholakia, Dholakia and Kshetri (2003) who reported low level of ICT competence among female teachers. Omenyi, Agu and Odimegwu (2007) attributed this finding to the societal role expectations of the African women which places a lot of restrictions on them. However, these findings were at variance with the work of Wong, Sidek, Aida, Zakaria, Kamariah, Hamidah and Hanafi (2005) who reported that females rated themselves to be more competent than males in ICT especially in inserting and editing texts for word processing, inserting texts and deleting slides for presentation, using search engines and downloading files from web and using e-mails for communication.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The survey design was adopted for this study. This design was appropriate because it dealt with the study of a large population by collecting and analyzing data from only a sample of the population.

Population of the Study

The population of the study consisted of 432 lecturers, teaching English in colleges of education and polytechnics in North West Zone Nigeria. A breakdown of the population revealed that there 245 English lecturers in the 12 colleges of education and 187 in the 12 polytechnics in the area of study.

Sample and Sampling techniques

A multistage sampling procedure was adopted to arrive at the sample size. They are stratified, proportionate and random sampling. First, stratified sampling technique was used to separate the population into two strata. i.e. polytechnics and colleges of education. The first stratum was made of 12 polytechnics with 187 English language teachers and the second stratum was made of 12 colleges of education with 245 English language teachers. The reason for using this technique was to give room for selecting sample proportionately. Secondly, proportionate sampling technique was used to select sample from each stratum based on its population size. In this case, the population size of each stratum was determined the number of samples to be drawn from that stratum as a fraction of the total population. Lastly, simple random sampling technique was used to select samples from each stratum. Therefore a total of 231 samples were selected for the study.

Research Instrumentation

The instrument used for data collection was structured questionnaire with a 4-points rating scale. The Elena's (2008) questionnaire for 'Evaluating the Use of ICT in Education' was adapted. It was designed to address research questions with regard to the Utilization of ICT Skills ICT skills among English language teachers of tertiary institutions in North West Zone of Nigeria. The items in the questionnaires were generated through a review of previous studies related to the study. It consisted of 2 parts; parts 1 demographic information of the respondents which include sex, age, rank, highest qualification, place of work, types of institution and length of service. Part 2 consisted of 18 items and they addressed issues on ICT utilization in teaching and learning among the English language lecturers in the area of study.

RESULTS

In testing the null hypothesis, Chi-square using SPSS analysis was used to find out the difference in the levels of ICT utilization among English language lecturers from Colleges of Education and Polytechnics. The result has been presented in tables as suggested by experts.

There may not be momentous difference in the level of ICT utilization between male and female English language lecturers in the Northwest Zone of Nigeria.

Chi-square statistical technique was used via SPSS analysis to test the null hypothesis, to find the differences in the utilization of ICT between male and female English lecturers. The result of the analysis was presented in tables.

It is concluded that majority of English lecturers in Colleges of Education and polytechnics have adequate knowledge on most of the ICT skills like power point presentation Microsoft word/excel, email, social media, overhead projector and internet. Other skills are language laboratory, sound system and radio/television assisted instructions which they gained through the various TETFund sponsored workshops, conferences, and trainings both locally and abroad.

The utilisation of ICT skills was relatively low. It was therefore concluded that lecturers of polytechnic and colleges of education in North West Zone of Nigeria do not effectively integrate ICT materials such as computers, internet, projectors etc. in the teaching and learning of English language.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Capacity Building for Lecturers: Regular ICT training workshops and seminars should be organized to improve lecturers' skills and confidence in using technology.
2. Provision of ICT Resources: Tertiary institutions should invest in ICT infrastructure, such as computers, internet facilities, and projectors, to create an enabling environment for ICT integration.
3. Policy Implementation by Regulatory Bodies: Organizations like NBTE and NCCE should enforce policies that promote ICT adoption in teaching and learning processes.
4. Monitoring and Evaluation: Institutions should establish monitoring mechanisms to assess and improve ICT utilization among lecturers.
5. Encouraging Collaboration: Lecturers should be encouraged to collaborate and share best practices in ICT usage to foster peer learning and innovation.

CONCLUSION

The study concludes that while English lecturers in polytechnics and colleges of education in Northwestern Nigeria possess basic ICT skills, their utilization of these tools in teaching remains low. Gender does not significantly influence ICT adoption, indicating that barriers to effective ICT integration are systemic rather than demographic. Enhancing ICT usage in these institutions is essential for improving teaching efficiency and meeting global educational standards.

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